

Late Recurrence of Giant Gastric Trichobezoar Manifested as Severe Upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding: Case Report and Brief Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Gastric trichobezoars are an uncommon clinical entity characterized by the progressive accumulation of ingested hair within the gastric cavity, commonly associated with trichotillomania and trichophagia. Clinical presentation is variable, ranging from chronic dyspeptic symptoms to potentially severe complications such as gastrointestinal obstruction, perforation, or gastrointestinal bleeding. Late recurrence after initial surgical treatment represents an exceptionally rare phenomenon.

Case presentation: A 43-year-old female patient with a previous surgical history of gastric trichobezoar at 20 years of age, as well as trichotillomania and trichophagia without active psychiatric follow-up, presented to the emergency department with asthenia, adynamia, fatigue, palpitations, and melena, associated with coffee-ground vomiting. Physical examination revealed a non-mobile indurated epigastric mass with decreased peristalsis. Laboratory studies documented severe anemia (hemoglobin 5.9 g/dL) and elevated nitrogenous waste products. Computed tomography demonstrated a large heterogeneous intragastric mass with near-complete occupation of the gastric chamber and antropyloric extension, consistent with a recurrent giant trichobezoar. Following hematologic stabilization with transfusion of four units of packed red blood cells and multidisciplinary inpatient management, an exploratory laparotomy with anterior gastrotomy and fragmented extraction of a 1,980 g gastric trichobezoar was performed. Postoperative evolution was satisfactory, with progressive reintroduction of oral intake and hospital discharge without complications.

Conclusions: Recurrent gastric trichobezoar may present decades after initial treatment and manifest atypically as severe upper gastrointestinal bleeding. Open surgery remains a safe and effective therapeutic strategy in cases of giant or complicated bezoars. Long-term psychiatric follow-up is essential to reduce the risk of recurrence.

KEYWORDS: Trichobezoar; Upper gastrointestinal bleeding; Trichotillomania; Trichophagia; Gastric surgery; Case report.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Published On:
15 June 2026

Available on:
<https://ijmscrs.com>

INTRODUCTION

Gastrointestinal bezoars are compact conglomerates of partially digested or undigested material that accumulate within the gastrointestinal tract, most frequently in the stomach due to its reservoir function and associated alterations in gastric motility and emptying (1, 2).

Based on their composition, they are primarily classified as phytobezoars, composed of plant fibers; trichobezoars,

formed from ingested hair; pharmacobezoars, secondary to the accumulation of medications or their excipients; and lactobezoars, composed of milk proteins, observed predominantly in infants (1, 3). Although they represent an infrequent clinical entity, they can cause potentially serious complications, including mucosal ulceration, gastrointestinal bleeding, intestinal obstruction, perforation, and peritonitis (1, 6).

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Within this classification, trichobezoar is a rare variant characterized by the progressive accumulation of hair in the gastric cavity. This material is resistant to both digestion and peristaltic propulsion, which favors its progressive compaction with mucus, food debris, and gastric secretions (1, 2).

This condition predominates in young women, with approximately 90% of reported cases occurring in females and a higher incidence in patients under 30 years of age. It is frequently associated with impulse control disorders, particularly trichotillomania and trichophagia, highlighting the importance of a multidisciplinary approach for its treatment and prevention of recurrences (5, 7, 8).

The clinical presentation of trichobezoar is usually insidious and variable, commonly manifesting with chronic abdominal pain, postprandial fullness, early satiety, nausea, vomiting, anorexia, and weight loss (1, 3).

As the mass increases in size, complications such as chronic anemia due to mucosal ulceration, upper gastrointestinal bleeding, gastric outlet obstruction, perforation, or distal extension into the small intestine, known as Rapunzel syndrome, can develop (1, 11).

In this context, computed tomography has proven to be a particularly useful diagnostic tool, allowing the identification of heterogeneous intraluminal masses with a characteristic mottled pattern due to trapped air bubbles, as well as more precisely defining their extent and any associated complications (2).

Treatment depends on the composition, location, size, and clinical impact of the bezoar. While some phytobezoars may respond to chemical dissolution or endoscopic fragmentation, trichobezoars have a low success rate with endoscopic management due to the density and cohesion of the hairy conglomerate (1, 12).

Consequently, surgical treatment remains the definitive strategy in giant, complicated, or recurrent cases, whether via a laparoscopic approach or open surgery (1, 12, 13).

We present the case of a 43-year-old woman with a history of surgery for gastric trichobezoar two decades earlier, associated with trichotillomania and trichophagia without active psychiatric follow-up, who developed a late recurrence of a giant gastric trichobezoar with atypical manifestations such as severe upper gastrointestinal bleeding and profound anemia, whose definitive management required open surgical resolution.

CASE DESCRIPTION

We present the case of a 43-year-old woman, a beneficiary of the Mexican Social Security Institute (IMSS), treated at Regional General Hospital No. 270 in Reynosa, with a surgical history of exploratory laparotomy for a gastric trichobezoar at age 23. Of significant psychiatric history, the patient had a known history of trichotillomania associated with trichophagia, without active psychiatric follow-up or

specialized treatment for an unspecified period. Additionally, she reported chronic use of ketorolac for persistent abdominal pain.

She reported abdominal pain since June 2023, located predominantly in the epigastrium and mesogastrium, of an intermittent nature, accompanied by a sensation of gastric fullness, nausea, and early satiety, without documented weight loss. Fifteen days prior to hospital admission, she began experiencing asthenia, adynamia, progressive fatigue, and palpitations. On the day of hospitalization, she developed multiple melena and an episode of coffee-ground vomiting, which prompted her to visit the emergency department at the end of March 2025. Upon admission, she was hemodynamically stable, with a heart rate of 95 beats per minute, blood pressure of 109/65 mmHg, and a respiratory rate of 20 breaths per minute. Physical examination revealed pallor of the skin and mucous membranes, as well as an indurated, non-mobile epigastric mass associated with decreased intestinal peristalsis. Laboratory studies documented severe anemia with hemoglobin of 5.9 g/dL, mean corpuscular volume of 82.5 fL, blood urea nitrogen of 33 mg/dL and urea of 70.6 mg/dL, findings compatible with upper gastrointestinal bleeding on an underlying chronic process.

During his initial stay in the emergency room, a nasogastric tube placement was attempted, but it was not properly installed. Subsequently, the abdominal computed tomography showed marked gastric distention secondary to a large heterogeneous intraluminal mass, with a mottled pattern and practically complete occupation of the gastric chamber, extending towards the antropyloric region, findings highly suggestive of recurrent giant gastric trichobezoar (Figure 1). The surgical history of previous trichobezoar, coupled with the history of trichophagia, allowed the preoperative diagnosis to be established.

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FIGURE 1. Contrast-enhanced abdominal computed tomography showing marked gastric distension secondary to a large, heterogeneous intraluminal mass, with a mottled pattern due to trapped air and almost complete occupation of the gastric chamber, consistent with a giant trichobezoar.

The patient received inpatient management with intravenous antisecretory therapy, close clinical monitoring, transfusion support with a total of four units of packed red blood cells, and consultations with the general surgery, gastroenterology, and psychiatry services; however, during her hospitalization, it was not possible to schedule an evaluation by the latter service. After two weeks of hematological optimization and clinical stabilization, definitive surgical intervention was scheduled.

In April 2025, an exploratory laparotomy was performed via a midline approach, revealing moderate postoperative adhesions and marked gastric distension. A wide anterior gastrotomy was performed, through which a large, compact mass consisting of densely packed dark hair mixed with food remnants and retained gastric contents was extracted by fragmentation (Figure 2). The mass was molded to the anatomy of the gastric cavity and extended to the pyloric region (Figure 3). The total weight of the extracted specimen was 1,980 grams (Figure 4). A systematic exploration of the small intestine was subsequently performed, revealing no distal extension of the bezoar or associated lesions. The gastrotomy was then closed in two layers without intraoperative complications.

FIGURE 2. Intraoperative removal of a gastric trichobezoar via anterior gastrotomy during exploratory laparotomy. A compact, hairy mass is observed occupying the gastric cavity.

FIGURE 3. Extraction of a trichobezoar molded to the anatomy of the gastric cavity.

FIGURE 4. Surgically extracted gastric trichobezoar, composed of hairy conglomerate and food remains, with an approximate weight of 1980 g.

The postoperative course was satisfactory. A liquid diet was initiated on the third postoperative day and was well tolerated,

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subsequently progressing to a soft diet without complications. The patient was discharged on the eighth postoperative day with a hemoglobin level of 8.2 g/dL and good tolerance of oral intake.

DISCUSSION

Trichobezoars are an uncommon clinical entity in surgical and gastroenterological practice (1, 6). They originate from the progressive accumulation of ingested hair within the gastric cavity. This material is highly resistant to both enzymatic digestion and peristaltic propulsion, which favors its compaction with mucus, food debris, and gastric secretions, gradually giving it the shape of the gastric chamber. Their classic presentation occurs predominantly in young women, with a strong association to trichotillomania and trichophagia, conditions that constitute the main pathophysiological substrate for their development (5, 7, 8). In this case, several unusual clinical elements stand out. First, the recurrence occurred two decades after the first surgical procedure, a considerably longer interval compared to most recurrences described in the literature, which are usually related to persistent compulsive behavior, poor adherence to psychiatric follow-up, and the absence of sustained multidisciplinary intervention. The patient's reported occasional episodes of trichophagia, coupled with the lack of specialized psychiatric treatment, likely led to a progressive reaccumulating of hair over the years, reaching enormous dimensions (7, 8).

This finding highlights that the apparent surgical resolution of the initial event does not, in itself, modify the underlying behavioral disorder; therefore, longitudinal mental health follow-up should be considered an integral part of definitive treatment.

A second relevant aspect concerns the clinical presentation. Although chronic abdominal pain, postprandial fullness, nausea, early satiety, and the presence of a palpable abdominal mass are relatively common manifestations in patients with trichobezoars, presentation as upper gastrointestinal bleeding with melena, coffee-ground emesis, and severe anemia is less frequent (1, 6).

In our patient, the absence of active bleeding or evident ulcerative lesions during surgery suggests that the hemorrhagic mechanism was likely multifactorial, secondary to chronic inflammation of the gastric mucosa due to sustained compression by the bezoar, transient pressure-induced superficial erosions, and a possible additional contribution from chronic ketorolac use, a recognized risk factor for gastroduodenal injury. The concomitant elevation of blood urea nitrogen (BUN) levels upon admission strengthened the clinical correlation with a recent upper gastrointestinal bleeding event.

From a diagnostic standpoint, computed tomography played a fundamental role by demonstrating a heterogeneous intraluminal mass with a mottled pattern and almost complete

filling of the gastric chamber, characteristic findings previously described in the literature (2).

Although upper gastrointestinal endoscopy is generally considered a valuable diagnostic tool, and even therapeutic in selected cases, in this instance the extent of the lesion, the impossibility of nasogastric tube placement, and the systemic clinical impact made it reasonable to prioritize hematological stabilization and definitive surgical intervention.

While some gastric bezoars may respond to conservative management, chemical dissolution, or endoscopic extraction, giant trichobezoars continue to pose a considerable therapeutic challenge due to the high cohesion of the hairy mass (1,12).

In this context, laparotomy with gastrotomy remains a safe, effective, and definitive approach, allowing for complete extraction, systematic inspection of the gastrointestinal tract to rule out distal extensions or satellite bezoars, and immediate resolution of the mechanical obstruction. In our patient, the fragmented removal of a 1,980-gram trichobezoar, with almost total occupation of the gastric chamber, confirms that a minimally invasive or endoscopic approach would hardly have been feasible or safe.

Although laparoscopic and even robotic-assisted approaches have recently been described for selected trichobezoars, open surgery remains the standard in giant masses with almost complete occupation of the gastric cavity and significant clinical impact (12, 13).

Finally, this case emphasizes the importance of a comprehensive multidisciplinary approach. Beyond successful surgical resolution, prevention of recurrence depends on timely recognition of associated behavioral disorders, early referral to specialized psychiatric care, and ongoing longitudinal follow-up. The absence of intervention on the underlying psychiatric component probably constitutes the main risk factor for late recurrence, even decades after initial treatment (7,8).

CONCLUSION

Recurrent gastric trichobezoar is a rare condition that can manifest decades after initial treatment and present with potentially serious complications, including upper gastrointestinal bleeding and severe anemia. This case underscores the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion in patients with a history of trichophagia, chronic obstructive gastrointestinal symptoms, and a palpable abdominal mass. Computed tomography is a key diagnostic tool for determining the extent of the lesion and planning treatment, while open surgery remains a safe and effective strategy for giant or complicated trichobezoars. Finally, specialized psychiatric evaluation and longitudinal follow-up should be considered essential components of comprehensive treatment to reduce the risk of long-term recurrence.

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